

MICROBE
the Microbiome
Biobanking (RI)
Enabler

3rd MICROBE project newsletter

(January 2025)

Dear colleagues, friends and innovators,

Welcome to our third project update! We are thrilled to share the latest developments and milestones with you. In this edition, you'll find:

- Some news on the successful conclusion of our second year and progress on our initial milestones
- MICROBE Experts Campaign - Introduction to talented MICROBE researchers
- Retrospect on MICROBE's participation in several key conferences

By the end of January 2025, we have finalised our second MICROBE project year. The project made further important steps towards achieving the stated objectives and results. For example, initial microbiome preservation trials were executed for soil, seed and marine samples and our consortium partners generated significant data sets that are currently being analysed. Based on these results, we will plan the validation trials and hopefully extrapolate meaningful learning that can be transferred to other microbiome samples.

We have also made significant progress in the establishment of the data infrastructure. Although not all of our data is publicly available, you can get the first impression of proposed solutions here:

Our transversal topics (addressing regulatory issues, standardisation and QC) have also made significant progress. In collaboration with external stakeholders (most notably EPSO WG plants and microbiomes (Plants and Microbiomes - EPSO) and Microbes-4-Climate consortium (Microbes4Climate) we have initiated discussions about needs and gaps and started to develop recommendations for addressing them. Furthermore, we are proud to announce that we have been granted observer status in several ISO committees.

Looking forward, we are excited to meet our Advisory Group members and get their feedback on our progress during our 2nd annual meeting in April 2025.

HELMHOLTZ MUNICH

rtD services
innovation | cooperation | inspiration

Funded by
the European Union

MICROBE Experts Campaign

MICROBE has designed a MICROBE Experts Campaign to promote the people behind MICROBE. The campaign is based on the teams of each project beneficiary and also focuses on promoting our young researchers and colleagues in their workspace. For this we produce videos, take photos and personal statements that are shared via the MICROBE social media channels and YouTube. The media will also be available on the MICROBE website.

In our 1st newsletter we started with a video with Dr. Sara Pipponzi (AIT) and a video with our Coordinator Dr. Tanja Kostic (AIT), in our 2nd newsletter, we presented Mag. Cornelia Stumptner and Dr. Katrin Panzitt (MUG). This 3rd newsletter presents our colleagues from Helmholtz-Center (HMGU) in Munich, Germany, Dr. Michael Schloter and Dr. Pamela Espindola Hernandez.

Dr. Michael Schloter (right side)

My name is Michael Schloter and I am responsible for WP2 in the frame of the MICROBE project. I am mainly interested in the interaction of environmental and human microbiomes and the ensuing consequences for our health. Our microbiome is indeed a key component of our health. It is strongly influenced by environmental microbiota, which interact with the microbiome of barrier organs like skin or respiratory system. Therefore, the reduced microbial diversity in the environment, resulting from climate- and global change, strongly impacts human – environment interactions, resulting in an increase in environmental diseases and infections. According to the planetary health concept the prevention of such diseases requires strategies which increase biodiversity in the environment. We identify key microbiota from the environment, which trigger our health, develop strategies to promote the abundance of those microbiota in urban and indoor environments and analyze consequences for our health. MICROBE plays a very important role in our research, as here we combine molecular analysis of microbiomes with the approach to cultivate keystone taxa, which might be further used for prevention or therapy of diseases.

Dr. Pamela Espindola Hernandez (left side)

My name is Pamela Espíndola-Hernández and I work as a postdoctoral researcher at the Comparative Microbiome Analysis group at Helmholtz Munich and am part of MICROBE WP2. Considering different perspectives and applying various methodologies, I aim to elucidate minimal microbial components of complex environmental samples. I apply bioinformatic tools combining comparative genomics and network theory to identify “microbial keystone taxa” that might help to prioritize targeted isolates to assemble representative synthetic communities (SynComs).

Link to the MICROBE website and related interview videos: **MICROBE Videos**

MICROBE aims to set up a community of relevant experts outside our consortium.

We invite you to register to our MICROBE Community and actively work with us.

Follow us!

Visit our website and register to our MICROBE Community

MICROBE events and news

Here, we present MICROBE events and workshops as well as events related to the areas we are working in.

MICROBE data workshop, Hinxton, UK

9th - 10th January 2025

In January 2025, an internal MICROBE WS was held to discuss the progress in the soil preservation trial and strategies for data analysis and interpretation and define the direction of future experimental phases in the project. The workshop was hosted by EMBL and involved MICROBE experts from AIT, DSMZ, CABI, HMGU, and EMBL.

The workshop marked a major milestone, as we are now in the exciting phase of generating the first substantial experimental datasets from the microbiome preservation trials. These datasets are set to play a critical role in advancing our understanding of the impact that preservation methods have on soil microbiomes.

The workshop has been very productive with new insights gained and plans laid out paving the way forward for this important use case.

MICROBE project details

Duration: 02/2023 – 01/2027

EU Funding: € 5,804,683,-

HE-GA-Nr.: 101094353

www.microbeproject.eu

MICROBE at scientific conferences

MICROBE has been presented at the **Phytobiomes Conference** with a poster and a flash talk by Matthew Ryan and Miguel Bonin (CABI) in 2024. Our coordinator Tanja Kostic (AIT) presented our MICROBE project at the **ECCO 2024 Meeting** in Bari, Italy. In addition, MICROBE has been promoted at the newly established **Food Systems Microbiome Conference** 2024 in Torino, Italy. An interesting poster presented by Enrique Sapena Ventura (EMBL-EBI) at the **Festival of Genomics** in UK, January 2025.

Conferences where MICROBE will be present

2nd Fermented Foods Forum in Malaga, Spain.

5-7 February 2025; Link to the event: [LINK](#)

European Biobank Week 2025 in Bologna, Italy.

13-16 May 2025; Link to the event: [LINK](#)

17th Symposium on Bacterial Genetics and Ecology, Bacteria drive our planet's health in Graz, Austria.

1-4 July 2025; Link to event: [LINK](#)